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Exploiting The Value Of Indigenous Knowledge For Sustainable Subsistence Agriculture Production In Okpuje Community

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ABSTRACT

The study concerns exploiting the value of indigenous knowledge for sustainable subsistence agriculture production in Okpuje community, Nsukka Local Government Area of Enugu state Nigeria. The study was conducted among the ten communities that make up Okpuje. The study was necessitated by the need to examine the community local based knowledge of continued subsistence farming under unfavorable environmental condition. Efforts towards the attainment of sustainable subsistence agriculture production have achieved little success as a result of over reliance and utilization of western system of knowledge. Indigenous knowledge is the knowledge system held by traditional community and is based on the experience and adaptation to local culture and environment, which is valuable especially in sustaining subsistence agriculture production. Therefore there is the need to exploit the value of this indigenous knowledge for sustainable subsistence agricultural production. To accomplish this study, it will adopt a qualitative approach. An interview was conducted, data sourced from primary and secondary sources. It was found out that indigenous knowledge is self-developed and relied upon to generate sustainable crop need to meet subsistence need. The finding revealed that community members also continue to sustain farming in their various localities through indigenous farming practices. The practice involved improvement of crop yield and seed variety storage for future planting seasons to achieve food security and abundant food supply at household level.

Keywords: Value, Indigenous knowledge, Sustainable, Subsistent Agriculture.

INTRODUCTION

Indigenous knowledge is a local knowledge acquired by the people through accumulation of experience. It has been in existence as old as man was seen on the surface of the earth. Indigenous knowledge is as old as man in Okpuje community. Maroyi (2012), noted that indigenous system of crop production emerged over century of cultural and biological evolution and represent the accumulated experience of indigenous farmers.

The farmers produce indigenous crops through knowledge of environmental condition and seasonal change without access to external output, capital and modern scientific knowledge. After centuries of cultural and biological evolution, communities have evolved local adaptive complex farming systems that have assisted them to produce and manage agricultural production to meet their subsistence needs. Indigenous crop production provides rural community with food resources.

By simple definition, Indigenous knowledge refers to a systematic body of knowledge acquired by local people through accumulation of experience, informal experience and understanding of their environment (Tella 2007). Therefore, sustainable subsistence agriculture can be achieved through the value of indigenous knowledge. Ontario, (2016) defines sustainable agriculture as farming in a

sustainable way, meeting society food and present need without compromising the ability of future generation to meet their needs.

Sustainable agriculture provides a potential solution that enable agricultural system to feed a growing population within the changing environmental condition, given the finite supply of natural resources of any specific location (Ontario 2016). A lot of crops are produced through indigenous knowledge system in Okuje which include yam of various species, water yam (*Dioscorea alata*, locally called abala), White yam (*Dioscorea Rotundata*, locally called abi), cocoyam (*Dioscorea esculenta*, locally called ede), cassava (*manicot esculenta*, locally called Alibo), groundnut (*arachishyprogea*, locally called opapa), melon (*citrullusvulgaria* locally called egusi), maize (*zea may* locally called azizi or oka), cowpea (*virgna sinensis*, locally called Akidi), the people are great garri producers, melon, maize, beans and so on. This is in agreement with Azum-Ali (2007) who affirms that production of indigenous crops form the basis of sustainable agriculture in sub-Sahara Africa. Food is produced from cereals, legumes, cucumber, cowpea and groundnut, millet, sorghum, gourd, melon and so on. These crops are produced in various locations by the community based farmers as abundant food sources. In Okpuje community plots of land near home and outside home called Agu are used for farming which provides household with a range of plant that serve as food.

It is observed that indigenous cereals provide food security to small scale farmers in the community because they are tolerant to poor soil, however subsistence farming is rapidly disappearing due to major social, political and economic change. (Mignet and Parviz 2008) posits that conservation and management of subsistence farming for sustainable agriculture production in community may be possible if they are linked to the preservation of the cultural diversity and economic viability of the local farming population.

Rock (1992) explains that many indigenous crops production system are characterized by low productivity and instability of production, marginal and erratic rainfall responsible for poor food productivity. Indigenous knowledge become relevant as it helps to generate sustainable crop yield to meet subsistence need. The knowledge is valuable for sustainable adaptation policies to assist rural communities which are vulnerable to climatic change. Indigenous knowledge enables its owners to engage in subsistence farming at the time of seasonal and climatic variability (FAO 2008). Subsistence farming is sustained through indigenous adaptation mechanism which Neid and Hug (2014) refer to as community based adaptive that can be defined as community led process based on communities priorities, needs, knowledge and capacities which should empower people to plan and cope with the impacts of climatic change.

The main thrust of this study is to examine various way of exploiting indigenous knowledge for sustainable agricultural production in Okpuje community Nsukka local government area of Enugu State Nigeria: specifically the objective of the study include to;

- i. Find out the meaning of indigenous knowledge
- ii. Examine community based local mechanism for sustainable subsistence farming under unfavorable environmental condition
- iii. Ascertain the value of indigenous knowledge for sustainable agriculture
- iv. Examine indigenous farming system that have help the community managed their food resources.

Information was collected using interview, observation and focused group discussion. Books, academic journals and public library, internet were relied upon for secondary data so as to complement data derived from primary sources.

The outcome of this study will enable community based farmers in Nigeria in general and Okpuje to be aware of their relevance and significant contribution in sustainable subsistence farming through the use of their indigenous knowledge.

Study Area

Okpuje is a town that is located at the North West end of Nsukka local government Area in Enugu state of Nigeria. It is on the trunk B road leading from Nsukka to Idah in Kogi state (Eze 2005). At her northern end Okpuje has a common boundary with Ibagwa- Agu in Nsukka local government Area, in the south Orobo-Abi in uzouwani local government Area of Enugu state and in the west Avurugo and Ugwuaka in Kogi state. It is situated on friendly landscape which is scheduled somehow by two hills, one at the north and the other at the south entering to the western part of the town.

Okpuje is within the deciduous forest area of Nigeria. Okpuje soil is fertile and very rich for the cultivation of yams and cassava among other crops. Being wholly within the tropics, therefore, rainfall determines the rhythm of economic activities in the area.

Economy

The primary occupation of Okpuje is farming as Okpe Clement observed. This can be attributed to the large expanse of agricultural farmland on which it is situated. A lot of farm crops such as yams of various species, cocoa, yam, cassava, (for which the people are great garri producers), melon, maize bean etc. are produced in the community.

A man is adjudged rich based on the abundance of agricultural crops he possesses by traditional standards. Wealth in itself confers honors and dignity. Consequently, people strive to be wealthy and since an individual, working alone can hardly acquire wealth, it makes people to marry as many wives as they could. Many children are born and large scale farming is practiced. More hands, more wealth and greater recognition was achieved.

Religion

According to Okoro Micheal, Okpuje people are deeply religious. They believe in the existence of Supreme Being called Ezechitoke Abiama (God the creator) who is the source of life. Atama Gabriel pointed out that apart from the main God, there is also a belief in a personal god called "chi" to which sacrifices are offered during good and bad times. Furthermore, there is a belief in a pantheon of deities like Ugwu-Okpuje, Asama, Ahimuze and Obata and sacred stones. The chief priest called Atama is in charge of the deities and ritual sacrifices. It is pertinent to note that Christianity and western education have impacted so much on their traditional religion that most of them today are Christians of various denominations.

Political Life

The administrative set up of Okpuje as Ugwu Christopher noted comprises the elders and Ama-title holders. The elders are in charge of administering civil duties in villages and they also handle minor criminal disputes.

The council of Ama-title holder is in charge of handling cases which the elders could not settle. They serve as the final court of appeal. This council also deals directly with serious criminal cases. In serious cases of sacrilege such as disclosing the secrets of masquerade to a woman, the culprit is tried and fined by the general council. Other cases such as witchcraft and poisoning are settled by drinking a liquid concoction from a tree called "Ohachi". The belief is that the innocent would vomit the whole substance and live while the one that is guilty shall die. The highest penalty that can be given is banishment. The Igwe-in-council is the paramount ruler while the Onyishi and representatives of each community form the leaders of the community

Conceptual Framework

Indigenous knowledge has defied common definition and as a result connotes different things to different people. It is widely recognized as knowledge that is possessed by local people, used for local level decision making especially in sustainable subsistence agriculture production. Dei (2000) defined indigenous knowledge as about the common sense ideas and cultural knowledge of local people concerning day to day life.

Indigenous knowledge is valuable to the way communities regard and live in their environment and presents communities with ways of managing their environment, be it natural, culture and political.

Adedipe et al (2004) defined indigenous knowledge as ethno-scientific, folk knowledge, traditional knowledge, local knowledge, people knowledge and so on. Warran (1987) posited that indigenous knowledge is a local knowledge that is unique to a given culture. According to Rajasekaran (1993) indigenous knowledge is the systematic body of knowledge acquired by local people through the accumulation of experiences, informal experiments, understanding of the environment in a given culture. In the words of Haverkort and De Zeeor (1992) it is the actual knowledge of a given population that reflects the experiences based on traditions and include more recent experiences with modern technology. From the above definition, indigenous knowledge can be seen as a body of

knowledge that deal with aspect of community beliefs, practices, skills and technology evolved without direct input from scientific knowledge.

Dei (2000) identified three broad aspect of indigenous knowledge. These include:

1. Traditional knowledge which is inter-generational knowledge passed from generation to generation
2. Empirical knowledge which is based on observations of the surrounding environment (nature, culture and society)
3. Revealed knowledge which is provided through dreams, visions and intuition.

Therefore indigenous knowledge is holistic and encompasses the physical and spiritual aspects of life. Tella (2007) saw the value of indigenous knowledge in sustainable agriculture production in the following way:

- Provides problem solving strategies in communities
- Contribute significantly to global development knowledge
- Valuable for development process and an under-utilized resources in the development process

Indigenous knowledge is viewed in some areas as the knowledge of the poor and illiterate.

Sustainable Agriculture

Sustainable agriculture can be defined in many ways; ultimately it seeks to sustain farmers' resources and communities by promoting farming practices and methods that are profitable, environmentally sound and good for communities. It rewards the true values of producers and their products. It also rewards the best practice of the past.

Sustainable agriculture is:

- Economically viable
- Socially supportive
- Ecologically sound (<https://www.westernsane.org>)

United States National Agriculture Research Extension and Teaching Policy Act of (1977), defined sustainable agriculture as an integrated system of plant and animal production practices having a site specific application that will over a long term.

- Satisfy human food and need
- Enhance environmental quality and the natural resources buried upon which the agriculture economy depends
- Make the most efficient use of non-renewable resources and farm resources and integrate where appropriate natural biological cycle and controls
- Sustain economic viability of farm
- Enhance the quality of life for farmers and society as a whole

Key principles outline by Jules prett for sustainable agriculture include;

- The incorporation of biological and ecological processes such as nutrient cycling, soil regeneration and nitrogen fixation into agriculture and food production practices
- Using the expertise of farmers to both productively work the land as well as to promote the self-reliance and self-sufficiency of farmers (Jules 2008)

Theoretical View Points

The debate on theoretical view point on sustainable agriculture centered on two different approaches. An exocentric approach and ethnocentric approach (Robinson 2009).

The ecocentric approach as argued emphasizes on how growth levels of human development and focuses on organic and biodynamic farming techniques with the goal of changing consumption pattern and resources allocation and usage.

The technocentric approach argued that sustainability can be attained through variety of strategies, from the view that state led modification of the industrial system like conservation or centered farming systems should be implemented, to the argument that bio technology is the best way to meet the increasing demand for food.

The theory of multifunctional is relevant in this study as the central argument of multi-functionality is that agriculture is multi-functional enterprise with other factors from the production of food and fibre, other function include renewable resources management, landscape conservation and biodiversity. (Renting et al 2009).

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Indigenous Knowledge for Subsistence Farming

The responses of Ezema Gabriel and Okpe Clement, on describing subsistence farming revealed that Okpuje community provide food for their families through production of indigenous crops from their land within and outside their home. They revealed that an individual has an average land of two hectare or more, while there are so many uncultivated land especially at Agu Okpuje. The people used indigenous skill and local tools for farming. Planting of crops generally commences after the first rain. The seeds of various crops are mixed and sown simultaneously to grow crops together in the farmland.

The cultivation system of the area represents long centuries of trial and error between man, the physical environment (climate and soil) and what may be termed his "biological auxiliaries" (plants animal and micro fauna) and upon which his survival and progress depend.

Farming system were representation of man's attempt to control and exploit his environment for his general food supply. This attempt leads in the application of the following farming system such as shifting cultivation, crop rotation, mixed cropping and mixed farming. One or more of this system must be employed by the farmer and his household.

Exploiting the value of indigenous knowledge for farming practices

According to Asogwa Jude indigenous community members use to sustain subsistence farming. The responses showed that community members uses their indigenous farming practices such as planting on different soil types, soil fertilization, selection and storage of seed and maintenance of crops in addition, to these knowledge system, Okpe revealed the impact of rainfall forecast by the people. This indigenous knowledge system is produced by local people based on their lived experience.

Food and agricultural organization (2008) attested to the above that local farmers and indigenous communities have indigenous knowledge, experience and practices related to sustainable agricultural production the people is use local of calendar to predict rainfall is as old as the community. The beginning of rain marked the sprouting of tree leaves and flower. The appearance of star, moon and the sun are carefully observed at the beginning of planting season, traditionally, it is believed that the signs of these celestial bodies denote good or bad harvest. Okpe a rainmaker at Okpuje said that it is believed that if the horn of the crescent moon point towards the earth, it puts rain, but if it point away from the earth it holds rain.

The indigenous use of rainfall forecasting is valuable as it helps indigenous farmers to plan for the planting season, whenever a bad season is predicted, farming will not be done until it rains very well. The people knowledge of rainfall corroborates Speranza et al (2010) findings that local farmers possess knowledge of the use of local indicators such as plant, birds, insects, and astronomy in predicting rainfall. Chang'a et al (2010) also showed that this type of indigenous knowledge is valuable in farm decision making to respond to anticipated poor yields. Orlore and Roncoll (2014) also noted that in Uganda farmers used local indicators such as plates and shapes of the moon to predict upcoming weather.

Knowledge of Soil Types

We can see that Okpuje people have knowledge of soil varieties by knowing colour and texture, and the type of crops that do well on a particular soil types. According to Okoro, Michael black clay soil is rich in nutrients and good for cultivation of maize, yam, cassava. Sandy soil and clayey soil is good for all crop. Sandy soil is good for black beans, groundnut, loamy soil is good for yam and cassava. Buthelezi and Hughes (2010) shared similar view that Zulu subsistence farmers have knowledge of soil based on color and texture of top soil, the dark soil indicate higher fertility while lighter soil signifies lower fertility

Soil Fertility

Ugwu Harison also discloses that they apply poultry manure and animal dung to make the soil fertile, retain moisture and avoid pests. This improves soil moisture conservation. In Tanzania Olatokun and Ayanbode (2011) noted also that if weeds are left to grow, they cover the soil, prevent it from heating up or drying out excessively induce a positive competition which stimulates crop growth and reduces erosion during rainfall.

Mulching

Ugwu Harison a local farmer opined that previous harvest residue in the form of maize stalks, groundnut leaves; dried bean and nut plants are good soil stabilizer. After the harvest the residue is filled with the soil to improve moisture retention and fertility of the soil.

Seed Selection

Seeds are carefully selected for planting in the next season after harvesting, good seed are selected by colour, only bright coloured and large sized seeds are selected for planting. Olatokun and Ayanbode (2010) again submitted that Nigeria women cut the seed and preserved them for the next planting season. In Ethiopia as Belenle and Singh (2012) pointed out that farmers select healthy crops in term of maturity, period, height, color and size, they are separated and dried carefully threshed and the grains are saved for replanting.

Multiple Cropping

The local farmers according to Ezeja incorporate a variety of crops with different growth habit in the same land to maximize the chance for production of multiple crops, sowing of seeds is done at random by hand. All seed varieties are sown in the same land. The practice maximize the growth of all crops at the same time in the land. Inter planting allows cropping systems to reuse their own stored nutrients, with the system productivity per unit area is higher than in mono cropping system with different growth habit management.

Maintenance of Crops

It was revealed that when the crops are about four weeks weeding starts. Weeds are removed by hand or hand-hoe to avoid them competing for moisture with the crops thereby disturbing the growth of crops. Adedipe et al (2014) in Tanzania argued that farmers regarded weed competition as negative for crop growth; they performed superficial hoeing and leave the weeds on the soil surface as protective mulch to recycle the nutrient and allow nitrogen assimilation through the bacteria decomposing the plants. In Okpuje we can see that when the crops are about maturing, the women, boys and girls spend days going to the farm scaring animals like rodents for planted groundnut, some use local trap, for the animals that use to eat the crops. Some make image of human beings with local materials to scare rodents in groundnut farm.

Storage of Seeds and Crops

After harvesting, the crops are stored and presented from attack by weevils and other insects. The most common preservation practice is by hanging the maize cobs on the kitchen roof in the olden days, they were hanged on hut roof. Yams are preserved and stored in a barn. The seed grains also are stored in bags, pots after drying them under the sun.

Land Fallowing

In many places exhausted lands are left fallow for two years or more, which fallowing enables local farmers capture the value of natural processes of soil regeneration typical of ecological succession. The use of green manure intensifies the old fallowing technique in area where long fallow period are not possible anymore.

Indigenous Knowledge for Environmental Conservation

Environmental conservation refers to the conservation of natural features including geographical and geo-morphological features flora and Fauna. Osunade (1994) noted that in Switzerland touch is an important process for farmers in deciding soil fertility, as well as identifying the presence of Fauna and Flora, for example earthworm casts are formed on nutrient rich soil but never in acidic soils. It is revealed that conservation practice is valuable to indigenous communities for generation to come as can be seen among Okpuje community forest like Ugwu Okpuje is considered as shines for gods of the land, where no one does farming work. This forest is in effect considered protected areas. This protected forest has multiple functions because they. It also influences other elements of the environment such as biodiversity forest conservation and land use. It therefore served as important for regeneration of flora and fauna conservation practices are very vital to indigenous community like Okpuje as they ensure the sustainability of natural resources in order to guarantee their availability for generations to come.

CONCLUSION

The study shows that indigenous knowledge is still valuable in the community. The knowledge is embedded in community tradition, knowledge of calendar, the appearance of the moon and star used to plan the planting of crops. The materials used to fertilize the soil, mulch, manage crops and the seeds are procured through indigenous knowledge. These are locally developed, always available, affordable and culture specific. The study concludes that subsistence farming is sustained by indigenous farming practice and environment conservation. The subsistence practice involves the improvement of soil structure maintenance of crops and selection and storage of seeds for regulating season and so on. The indigenous knowledge is community developed and relied upon what to generate sustained crops yield to meet subsistence need.

The indigenous knowledge could be valuable toward achieving food security. The knowledge could also contribute to sustainable agricultural and adaptation policies to help rural communities which are vulnerable to climate change.

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